

Quinolinium Bromochromate : A New, Selective and Efficient Reagent for the Oxidation of Alcohols in Anhydrous Acetic Acid

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The selective oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds is an important reaction. For this transformation, a wide variety of chromium(VI) reagents are available in the literature¹. An attempt has been made here to synthesis a new oxidising agent by following the procedure reported for the preparation of other halochromates with a view to expand this area of synthetic utility².

Here, quinolinium bromochromate (QBC) has been used as a selective and efficient reagent which oxidises primary and secondary alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds in anhydrous acetic acid medium at room temperature (28–30°) without involving any side-reaction as indicated in the following scheme :

This reagent has certain advantages over other oxidising agents with respect to the following facts. Unlike other halochromates, it is quite stable at room temperature, highly selective in the oxidation of alcohol, less hygroscopic and not photosensitive. It requires comparatively shorter reaction time with higher yield. The results (Table 1) with quinolinium bromochromate suggest that this reagent is a valuable addition to the existing oxidising agents. Further investigation using this reagent is in progress.

Experimental

Quinolinium bromochromate : To chromium(VI) oxide (10 g, 0.1 mol) dissolved in water (15 ml) was cooled to 0°, was added 48% hydrobromic acid (17 ml, 0.1 mol) slowly with vigorous stirring. Quinoline (13 ml, 0.1 mol) was then added dropwise during 10 min to

TABLE 1 – OXIDATION OF ALCOHOLS

Substrate	Product*	Time h	Yield** %	Derivative# m p (°C)	
				Found	Reported
n-Butanol	n-Butanal	2	80	122	123 ^a
2-Heptanol	2-Heptanone	5	71	88	89 ^a
2-Decanol	2-Decanone	6	78	124	126 ^b
Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	5	89	161	162 ^a
Benzyl alcohol	Benzaldehyde	2	94	237	237 ^a
1-Phenylethanol	Acetophenone	8	88	245	250 ^a

*Products characterised by ir spectra and b.p. ** Yields determined by GC; all yields refer to isolated products.

#Product identified through ^a2,4-DNP derivative ^bsemicarbazone derivative

yield a brown solid. The reaction mixture was cooled for 2–3 h and the resulting dark brown crystals were dried under reduced pressure for 1 h at room temperature (yield, 19 g), m. p. 154–56° (Found : N, 4.3 C₉H₇NHCrO₃Br requires : N, 4.5%); ν_{max} (KBr) 950, 747, 605, 523, 465, 383, 350 cm⁻¹; chromium content was determined iodometrically (assay > 99%).

Procedure for the oxidation of alcohols : The substrate (alcohol, 0.01 mol) was added to a stirred suspension of QBC (0.015 mol) in purified anhydrous acetic acid (18 ml) with constant stirring at room temperature for the time period indicated in Table 1. The reaction mixture was then diluted with ice-water (150 ml) and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with aqueous NaHCO₃ followed by water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and filtered through a short column of silica gel. The contents of the column were washed with ether which on evaporation gave a clear solution. It was then distilled to yield the products.

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